

A Review on Federated Learning Frame work for Medical Image Analysis

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Abstract— Now a days people are visiting hospitals frequently from their middle age due to different diseases after covid-19. They get their health conditions check through medical images. Non-Government medical organizations are maintaining the datasets for patient's digital images. MRI Scanning is most useful for identification of many diseases. All MRI images are storing in data sets in DICOM Format only. Medical image security in India is demanding. The images help Physicians for future treatment and provide an accurate diagnosis without the need for presumptuous procedure. Digital images are available in DICOM format only. Up to now, research surveys not constructed efficient federated learning framework for medical images. in this study we have to find out the best suitable framework and provide high security to medical images though SHA 1024 algorithm.

Keywords— Federated Learning, SHA 1024, and DICOM

Introduction----Now a day's middle age people are suffering with different diseases. Everybody visits hospitals at least twice in a year and checking their health conditions with medical images. Non-Government medical organizations are maintaining the datasets for patient's digital images. MRI Scanning is most useful for identification of many diseases. All MRI images are storing in data sets in DICOM Format only. Medical image security in India is demanding. The images help Physicians for future treatment and provide an accurate diagnosis without the need for presumptuous procedure. The main aim of this work is to provide high security to the digital images. in this work, Digital images are available

in DICOM format only. DICOM format is international format for retrieving, transmitting, storing the images. From DICOM format we can convert medical images to Joint Photographic Experts Group (JPEG) or Tagged image file format (TIFF) or Graphics interchange format (GIF) or Portable networks graphics (PNG) formats of MRI Digital images. But in this work, we have to convert the DICOM format to Joint photographic experts Group (JPEG) format image with the size of 256 X 256 with 16 bits per pixel and file size must be 131 kb only. And then we are storing this digital image [3] in a data set of high secured cloud with horizontal federated learning framework.

In this process, we have to collect MRI Digital images hexadecimal values and are given to SHA 1024 algorithm. The hexadecimal values of the cipher text is an image and stored in cloud servers. We have to create a framework with horizontal federated learning approach [2] data set in cloud for storing all digital images of patients in it. So that when we need any digital image then we can fetch patients scanned MRI digital images and can download it with the credentials & provided by us. Then, only authenticated users can access the data. In this process, storing images and retrieving it from cloud also cost effective [1] and there is no safety for digital record of medical images. Hospital management system also get security issues for exchanging the medical images. Medical image analysis has been greatly pushed forward by computer vision and machine learning [1]–[4]. The remarkable success of modern machine learning methods, e.g., deep learning [5], can be attributed to the building and release of grand-scale natural image databases, such as ImageNet [6] and Microsoft Common Objects in

Context (MS COCO) [7]. Unlike natural image analysis, the field of medical image analysis still faces the fundamental challenge of the “small sample-size” problem [8], [9]. Based on small sample data, it is difficult for us to estimate real data distributions, greatly hindering the building of robust and reliable learning models for medical image analysis. An intuitive and direct solution to this small sample size problem is to pool images from multiple sites together and build larger datasets to train high quality machine learning models. However, sharing medical imaging data between different sites is intractable due to strict privacy protection policies such as Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) [10] and General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [11]. For example, the United States HIPAA has rigidly restricted the exchange of personal health data and images [10]. Thus, directly sharing and pooling medical images across different sites/datasets is typically infeasible in real-world practice

Fig. 1. Overview of federated learning (FL) for medical image analysis, including a server and multiple clients. Each selected client trains a model on its local dataset. The server collects the local models and calculates a global model that is broadcast to all the selected clients for deployment

As a promising solution for dealing with the small-sample size problem and protecting individual privacy, federated learning [12]–[14] has become a spotlight research topic in recent years, which aims to train machine learning models in a collaborative manner without exchanging/sharing data among different sites. As an emerging machine learning paradigm, federated learning deliberately avoids demand for all the medical data residing in one single site. Instead, as shown in Fig. 1, it depends on model aggregation/fusion techniques to jointly train a global model which is then sent/broadcast to each site for fine-tuning and deployment. There have been several survey papers on federated learning [15]–[20], but further technical details about facilitating federated learning in medicine and healthcare are not yet covered. Several recent surveys introduce the applications of federated learning in medicine and healthcare areas [21]–

[25]. However, some of them focus on electronic health records [21], [22] or internet of medical things [26], without paying attention to medical imaging. And some survey papers cover very broad areas [23], [24], without detailed introduction on federated learning in medical image analysis.

BACKGROUND

Network security is more important for Future of AI and data science.[1] Cloud-based medical image sharing platforms are increasingly becoming more prevalent in medicine. Ultimately online medical image transfer systems allow physicians to build better and deeper referral networks, which in turn mean increased volumes and a more open platform for collaboration. Federative learning provides high security for image processing applications [3] In medical information systems, image data can be considered crucial information. As imaging technology and methods for analyzing medical images advance, there will be a greater wealth of data available for study. Hence, protecting those images is essential. Image

encryption methods are crucial in multimedia applications for ensuring the security and authenticity of digital images. Recently, the encryption of medical images has garnered significant attention from academics due to concerns about the safety of medical communication medical image analysis is crucial for the efficient diagnosis of many diseases. Hospitals maintain vast repositories of images, which can be leveraged for various purposes, including research [4], FL can help clinicians to diagnose diseases and support medical decisions more efficiently and robustly. Analyzing the medical images are need for diagnosing the diseases [2] , need to provide security and storing

in cloud is very useful for accessing from different sources are need for better diagnosis of different diseases

A traditional way to train machine learning models is to use medical images from a specific site/dataset, with at least two drawbacks.

(1) Due to the cost of imaging and labeling, the amount of images in local datasets is usually small (e.g., tens or hundreds) which is not enough to train a model with good generalizability. This is the well-known “small sample- size” problem [8], [9]. This problem may lead to sub-par learning performance of a model, and produce results that lack statistical significance.

(2) Data from a specific site/dataset may be biased in distribution and not representative of the true data distribution. It is not unusual that medical sites contain unbalanced data. For example, in some sites, healthy subjects significantly outnumber the patients which may lead to a biased model towards the healthy ones. Federated learning helps address these limitations, aiming to “pool” medical images together in a distributed way, thereby greatly increasing the sample size. This can effectively take advantage of available data from multiple sites to enhance the statistical power of machine learning models.

1) Medical images from different sites/datasets are typically acquired by different scanners or scanning protocols.

2) Patients in different sites/hospitals have different distributions. The heterogeneous data distribution, i.e., “domain shift” or “client shift”, may cause significant degradation or biased performance of a federated learning system. How to alleviate the negative influence of data heterogeneity is one of the most important and challenging research problems for federated

2) Privacy Leakage/Poisoning Attacks:

In classic FL, only the model parameters (e.g., weights) are exchanged and updated without data sharing. This is considered an effective way of privacy protection. But further research reveals that FL still faces privacy and security risks, including privacy leakage [81]–[83] and poisoning attacks [166], [167]. These issues can happen at both the server end and the client end. Since an FL system contains the communication and interaction of many entities/parties, how to effectively protect individual privacy and data security is a very challenging problem.

3) Technological limitations:

While a majority of research is centered on algorithm design for various medical applications, the practical implementation of FL systems encounters significant technological hurdles. For instance, certain FL algorithms demand substantial computational resources, posing challenges for the underlying hardware infrastructure. Furthermore, addressing communication costs, optimizing network resource allocation, and ensuring synchronization are all formidable obstacles when striving to construct a robust and functional FL system in real life.

Fig. 1. Overview of federated learning (FL) methods for medical image analysis

Challenges of FL for Medical Image Analysis

1) Data Heterogeneity Among Clients:

Data heterogeneity is widespread in real-world medical image sites. Such heterogeneity can hardly be avoided in practice due to the following factors.

4) Long-Term Viability of FL-based Medical Image Analysis:

Federated Learning is not just a novel machine learning algorithm; it represents a dynamic and systematic approach to engineering. It is imperative to focus on the long-term viability of FL systems when applied to medical image analysis. This involves addressing critical issues such as scalability, sustainability, and evolving regulations. In real-world scenarios, unforeseen

challenges emerge, such as clients leaving or joining the training process, as well as unexpected technical and connectivity issues. Effectively arranging an FL system for robust and stable long-term medical image analysis is a complex endeavor.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we review the recent advances in federated learning (FL) for medical image analysis. We summarize existing FL methods from a system view and categorize them into client-end, server-end, and client-server communication methods. For each category, we provide a novel “question-answer” paradigm to elaborate on the motivation and mechanism of different FL methods in medical image analysis. We also introduce existing software tools/platforms and benchmark medical image datasets that have been used for federated learning. In addition, we conduct an experiment to empirically compare different FL methods on a popular benchmark imaging database (i.e., ADNI). We further discuss current challenges, potential research opportunities, and future directions of FL-based medical image analysis. We hope that this survey paper could provide researchers with a clear picture of the recent development of FL in medical image analysis and that more research efforts can be inspired and initiated in this exciting research field.

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